

COST Action
Safety in the Game Meat Chain (SafeGameMeat)
CA22166
Workshop Report

HEALTH RISKS AND BIOAVAILABILITY OF METAL RESIDUES FROM HUNTING AMMUNITION IN GAME MEAT

Billund, Denmark – September 10–11, 2024

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Abstract

The workshop "Health Risks and Bioavailability of Metal Residues from Hunting Ammunition in Game Meat," held in Billund, Denmark, explored the pressing issue of lead contamination in game meat. Experts from various disciplines discussed the health risks posed to humans and wildlife, the environmental impacts of lead residues, and potential alternatives to lead-based ammunition. Key findings highlighted the bioavailability and toxicity of lead from ammunition, the range and possibilities of current non-lead alternatives, and the need for harmonized regulations across Europe. The workshop underscored the importance of hunter education, public awareness, and interdisciplinary research to facilitate the transition to non-toxic ammunition and reduce contamination. Recommendations include stronger enforcement of lead bans, targeted outreach to stakeholders, and comprehensive risk assessments for alternative materials. These efforts aim to ensure the sustainability of hunting practices and the safety of game meat in the food chain.

Keywords: Lead contamination, hunting ammunition, game meat, bioavailability, health risks, non-lead alternatives, environmental impact, regulation, food safety, hunter education.

Introduction

The workshop "Health Risks and Bioavailability of Metal Residues from Hunting Ammunition in Game Meat" was held in Billund, Denmark, on September 10-11, 2024, as part of COST 22166, "SafeGameMeat", a European collaborative initiative aimed at promoting research and fostering cooperation to ensure the safety and sustainability of game meat in the food chain. This event brought together a diverse group of experts including toxicologists, veterinarians, chemists, food safety specialists and wildlife researchers to discuss the pressing issue of metal contamination in game meat, particularly from hunting ammunition. The workshop focused on assessing the human and environmental health risks posed by metal residues, strategies for transitioning away from lead ammunition, and public perceptions of these risks. Discussions highlighted several misconceptions, including the belief that non-lead ammunition is less effective or unsafe for hunting, and a general underestimation of the health risks posed by lead residues in game meat. Understanding these attitudes is critical to developing effective communication and education strategies to facilitate change.

This report summarizes the discussions, presentations and conclusions of the workshop. The goal of the workshop was to provide a comprehensive analysis of the current state of knowledge regarding metal contamination in game meat, identify knowledge gaps, and propose actionable recommendations to mitigate these risks. Particular emphasis is placed on the bioavailability and toxicity of metals such as lead, copper, tin and bismuth, as these metals are either widely used in hunting ammunition or present unique challenges and risks. Lead, for example, is highly toxic and poses significant health risks to both humans and wildlife, while copper and tin, while considered safer, still present concerns related to fragmentation and bioavailability in game meat. Bismuth, a common non-lead alternative, requires further research to assess its long-term environmental and health effects. These considerations underscore the need for careful evaluation of alternative materials. By integrating findings from scientific research and policy discussions, the report aims to inform stakeholders, including policy makers, hunters, and researchers, about ways to reduce health risks and environmental contamination from hunting ammunition residues.

1. Ammunition and Health (Chair: Maciej Durkalec)

1.1. What is game meat, and how can ammunition metal affect it?

Niels Kanstrup (Aarhus University, Denmark)

The opening presentation, led by Niels Kanstrup from Aarhus University, focused on defining game meat and exploring the pathways through which hunting ammunition can lead to contamination. Game meat, as defined during the session, refers to edible tissues derived from wild birds and mammals traditionally hunted and consumed in Europe. This includes muscles and organs such as liver and heart, which are culturally and nutritionally important in the region. Participants discussed the nuances of this definition, including which species, tissues and consumer groups (such as humans and pets) should be considered within its scope.

A major focus of the presentation was the risk posed by metals in hunting ammunition, particularly lead. Lead's tendency to fragment on impact results in widespread contamination of game meat. Niels highlighted studies showing that lead levels in minced pheasant meat reached 122 mg/kg after exposure to lead pellets, compared to 0.033 mg/kg in controls (Kanstrup, 2012). Such contamination risks increase significantly during meat processing, as the grinding process disperses microscopic lead particles throughout the meat. X-rays of game have shown the extensive fragmentation patterns of lead bullets, with particles scattered far beyond the wound channel. Even bonded lead bullets, which are designed to minimise fragmentation, have been shown to release large amounts of fragments into tissue, contradicting the claims of the ammunition industry.

Non-lead alternatives such as bullets made from bismuth-tin alloys, tungsten or solid copper have been discussed as potential solutions. However, these alternatives are not without their challenges (Thomas, 2019). For example, while tin bullets are lead-free, they also fragment extensively, raising questions about their safety and environmental impact. Copper bullets showed much less fragmentation, with almost full weight retention, reducing the risk of contamination. However, participants noted that rigorous research is needed to fully understand the long-term toxicity and ecological impact of all non-lead materials.

Environmental concerns were also addressed. Lead residues from ammunition persist in ecosystems, posing a risk to scavengers and predators that consume contaminated carcasses or offal. The ingestion of lead shot by birds, particularly in wetlands, is well documented, resulting in lead poisoning with serious ecological consequences. Participants noted that around 95% of shotgun pellets fired during hunting end up in habitats, contributing to contamination of wildlife, soil, water and food chains.

The effectiveness of regulatory measures in reducing lead contamination was illustrated by the Danish ban on lead shot for waterfowl hunting (Kanstrup and Balsby, 2019). This policy significantly reduced lead residues in the environment, demonstrating the potential of well-enforced regulations to address contamination. However, challenges remain, including ensuring compliance and addressing hunters' misconceptions about the performance and safety of non-lead ammunition.

Hunter perspectives were explored through survey data, which revealed mixed attitudes towards non-lead ammunition (Kanstrup et al., 2021). While many hunters recognised its environmental benefits, concerns about cost, ballistic performance and perceived risks remained prevalent. A significant proportion of hunters expressed scepticism or resistance towards using non-lead ammunition, often due to limited information or misconceptions. Participants stressed the importance of education and outreach to dispel myths and promote understanding of non-lead alternatives. Effective communication to both hunters and the general public, combined with regulatory incentives, was suggested as a way to encourage uptake.

Discussions also focused on the ballistic properties of ammunition and their influence on fragmentation and contamination. Bullet design, construction and impact velocity were highlighted as critical factors in determining the release of metal fragments into game meat. While bonded bullets are marketed as reducing fragmentation, evidence presented by Niels showed that even these can release significant amounts of lead. In contrast, monolithic copper bullets showed minimal fragmentation and high residual weight, underlining their potential as a safer alternative.

Concerns have been raised about other metals used in ammunition, such as bismuth, tin, antimony and tungsten (Thomas, 2019). Although a shift to the use of these metals will reduce lead exposure, and despite the fact that most present alternatives are not of direct concern in relation to poisoning of wildlife, ecosystems and human consumers, there remains the need for authorities to raise awareness and establish benchmarks for the composition of all present and future products (Kanstrup 2024). Participants called for comprehensive assessments of all metals used in ammunition to ensure their safety for human consumption and ecological health.

The issue of lead in ammunition primers was briefly discussed. While primarily of concern in indoor or high-volume shooting ranges, the presence of lead and other toxic substances in primers warrants further attention. Some manufacturers have begun to develop lead-free primers, but their environmental and health impacts remain unclear.

The session concluded with a call for further research and collaboration. Participants emphasised the need for evidence-based approaches to assessing the risks associated with both lead and non-lead ammunition. Bioavailability studies, such as those using in vitro digestion systems (Paulsen et al., 2015a), were highlighted as essential for understanding how metals behave during cooking and storage. The importance of cross-disciplinary efforts to address gaps in knowledge on fragmentation patterns, residue fate and toxicity was underlined.

The collective insights from the session reinforced the importance of balancing sustainable hunting practices with the protection of human health and ecosystems. Participants agreed that a combination of regulatory measures, hunter education and scientific research is essential to achieve this goal. By addressing the technical, environmental and societal dimensions of ammunition-related contamination, the workshop set the stage for informed decision-making and policy development to promote safer hunting practices.

1.2. What Metals Are Used in Hunting Ammunition?

Peter Paulsen (University of Veterinary Medicine Vienna, Austria)

Peter Paulsen provided an in-depth overview of the metals used in hunting ammunition, highlighting their impact on food safety, environmental contamination and animal welfare. Peter approached the topic from a food science perspective, focusing on the fragmentation and corrosion of metals in game meat and their potential hazards.

Peter began by explaining how metal fragments from hunting ammunition can pose a dual hazard: physical hazards (sharp or large fragments causing injury) and chemical hazards (corroded metals releasing harmful substances). He presented X-ray images of minced game and pet food, showing metal fragments resembling bullet fragments. Depending on their size and composition, these fragments can corrode in the digestive system, releasing metals into tissues and posing food safety concerns.

He extended this discussion to environmental contamination, using an image of chewed military cartridges as a metaphor for how animals, such as wild boar, might inadvertently ingest materials deposited in their habitats. Although this example was military-specific, it underlined the broader issue of the ecological footprint of ammunition.

Peter's presentation also detailed the historical evolution of bullet materials and designs. Traditionally, lead was the primary material due to its density and malleability. Over time, technological advances introduced jacketed bullets, combining lead cores with harder outer materials such as copper to reduce fouling and improve performance. Despite these refinements, lead remains a significant source of contamination as it fragments extensively on impact. This has led to the development of bullets made of alternative materials such as copper, tin and bismuth, which are increasingly being used in lead-free ammunition (Paulsen et al., 2015b).

A comprehensive comparison of metals identified four main components in modern lead-free bullets: copper, iron, zinc and tin. While these metals are less toxic than lead, they are not without risks. For example, tin bullets often fragment severely, dispersing small particles throughout the meat, raising concerns among food safety professionals (Paulsen et al., 2015a). Copper, widely used in non-lead ammunition, is generally considered safer, but studies show that even copper bullets can release microparticles near the wound channels, resulting in localised contamination (Irschik et al., 2013; Schuhmann-Irschik et al., 2015). These findings highlight the need for careful evaluation of alternative materials. These findings highlight the need for careful evaluation of alternative materials and thoughtful approaches to reducing the risks associated with ammunition. One such strategy is the "3R" approach, which includes refinement, reduction and replacement in the design of hunting ammunition. Refinement involves the use of bonded bullets, where the lead core is securely welded to the jacket to minimise fragmentation. Reduction focuses on designing bullets with smaller lead cores or limiting lead to the tip. Replacement promotes non-lead alternatives such as monolithic designs or non-lead cores to eliminate lead exposure altogether.

Peter presented data comparing the copper content near gunshot wounds caused by lead and non-lead bullets (Irschik et al. 2013). Non-lead bullets generally released less harmful residues, but still contributed to elevated copper levels in localised tissue. He warned that while copper is essential for human health in small amounts, excessive concentrations can be problematic, particularly in regions close to the wound.

The presentation also examined the potential for metal corrosion during meat processing and cooking. Studies have shown that acidic marinades, such as vinegar or wine, can accelerate

the leaching of copper from embedded fragments (Schuhmann-Irschik et al., 2015). Although copper leaching is usually small, it highlights the need to understand how processing and cooking affect the behaviour of metal residues in game meat.

Peter emphasised the importance of mass-retaining slugs, such as monolithic copper designs, which fragment less and leave minimal residue in both meat and the environment. He also commended the performance of brands such as Barnes, which demonstrated superior mass retention and minimal fragmentation. However, he noted that while tin-core bullets are less toxic, they exhibit high fragmentation, which complicates their safety profile.

The discussion also highlighted the challenges of enforcing legislation and promoting the acceptance of non-lead ammunition. Peter stressed that while legislation is essential, it cannot replace awareness and education. Hunters need to recognise the risks associated with lead and other metals, not only to consumers, but also to wildlife and ecosystems. He called for collaborative efforts to raise consciousness among hunters and the public, noting the need for both regulatory and voluntary approaches.

Key points from the discussion:

- **Regulatory gaps:** The lack of standardised EU regulations for metal limits in game meat makes monitoring difficult. While countries such as Austria and Poland have national action levels, these vary widely. Participants called for harmonised regulations across Europe, taking into account both chemical and physical hazards, as well as the heterogeneous distribution of ammunition residues in the carcass, which complicates the interpretation of monitoring results.
- **Toxicity of alternative metals:** Concerns were raised about the lack of rigorous toxicity testing for new materials in Europe. In contrast, the US and Canada require extensive evaluations before new types of ammunition are approved. The group recommended the adoption of similar protocols to ensure safety and environmental compatibility.
- **Consumer perception:** The challenges of marketing venison containing lead residues were discussed. Consumers increasingly associate lead with poor quality and unsafe meat, creating a strong incentive for hunters to switch to lead-free alternatives to maintain market viability.
- **Pet food concerns:** Studies have shown that grinding processes in pet food production increase lead contamination by dispersing metal fragments. This highlights the need for tighter controls in the pet food industry, which often uses lower quality meat, including damaged or heavily contaminated game.
- **Hunter myths and resistance:** Participants identified widespread myths among hunters, such as the belief that copper bullets pose a greater risk due to over-penetration of carcasses and injuries from ricochets. These misconceptions, often perpetuated by pro-lead advocates, highlight the need for education and transparent communication.
- **Geographical and contextual variability:** Peter emphasised the importance of tailoring solutions to specific hunting contexts. For example, high velocity ammunition suitable for alpine areas may not be necessary in lowland areas where hunters typically shot at shorter distances. He argued for pragmatic approaches that achieve overall reductions in lead use without imposing universal mandates.

The session concluded with a call for further research and lobbying. Participants agreed on the importance of refining existing alternatives, conducting comprehensive risk assessments, and filling knowledge gaps, particularly on fragmentation patterns and metal bioavailability. They also highlighted the need to raise public and hunter awareness through educational campaigns and incentives to ensure a smoother transition to safer non-lead ammunition.

2. Human Health Risks (Chair: Rafael Mateo)

2.1. Risks to Human Health from Lead Residues in Game Meat

(Debbie Pain and Rhys Green, University of Cambridge)

The presentation provided a comprehensive overview of the risks to human health associated with lead residues in game meat, focusing on lead ammunition contamination and its consequences for frequent consumers.

Lead is a naturally occurring toxic heavy metal with no biological role and harmful effects on all body systems. It has historically been used in petrol, paint and water systems, but its use has been largely phased out in most developed countries since the 1970s due to stringent regulations. Despite this progress, dietary exposure to lead ammunition remains largely unregulated and poses significant risks, particularly to vulnerable populations such as children, pregnant women and frequent consumers of wild game.

Lead enters the human body primarily through ingestion, with absorption occurring in the gastrointestinal tract, particularly the duodenum (Collin et al., 2022). The amount absorbed depends on several factors, including the size and chemical composition of the lead particles, the nutritional status of the individual and the contents of the gastrointestinal tract. Once absorbed, lead circulates in the bloodstream and is distributed to soft tissues, including the liver and kidneys, where it remains for short to medium periods. Over time, lead is deposited in bones, where it can accumulate for decades and be remobilised during periods of physiological stress, such as pregnancy or ageing. Blood lead levels, which reflect recent exposure, have been widely studied because of their well-documented relationship with health outcomes (Gundacker et al., 2021).

The presentation highlighted that blood lead levels in Europe have declined significantly over the past few decades, largely due to reductions in environmental lead exposure. For example, geometric mean blood lead levels in young adults in Münster, Germany, declined from 7.87 µg/dL in 1981 to 1.04 µg/dL in 2019, reflecting broader trends across Europe (Lermen et al., 2021). This decline has allowed researchers to detect health effects at lower and lower blood lead levels, with evidence now showing that there is no safe threshold for lead exposure. The U.S. Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has progressively lowered the blood lead levels of concern for children over time, with the current reference level set at 3.5 µg/dL (CDC, 2021). Lead disproportionately affects children, who absorb more lead than adults due to their developing nervous systems and greater reliance on calcium, which lead chemically mimics. Cognitive impairments such as reduced IQ are among the most serious effects and appear to be irreversible (ATSDR, 2020; Cecil et al., 2008).

Lead residues in game meat result primarily from the fragmentation of lead ammunition on impact. When a lead bullet or shot hits a target, it fragments into numerous particles that are widely dispersed throughout the carcass (Leontowich et al., 2022). These fragments have been observed by X-ray and micro-CT imaging to extend well beyond the wound channel, with elevated lead concentrations detected up to 30 centimetres away (Dobrowolska and Melosik, 2008; Green et al., 2022; Pain et al., 2010). This pattern of contamination makes it impossible to remove all lead residues from game meat using standard butchery practices. In the case of small game such as pheasants, the problem is particularly acute because the small size of the lead shot results in widespread dispersal that cannot be effectively controlled (Pain et al., 2022). Even in large game such as deer, CT imaging have shown that significant amounts of lead remain in the meat even after removal of visibly damaged tissue (Haase et al., 2023).

Across Europe, the average lead concentration in game meat is around 2.5 mg/kg, which is 25 times higher than the European Union's maximum permitted level of 0.1 mg/kg for other meats such as beef, pork and poultry (European Commission, 2023). While Denmark has reduced lead levels through regulatory measures, lead levels in game meat have increased in many other European countries in recent years (Pain et al., 2022). Studies confirm that the main source of lead in game meat is ammunition rather than environmental contamination. For example, pheasants shot with lead ammunition have been found to contain significantly higher levels of lead than those shot with steel or bismuth alternatives, although some bismuth shot has also been found to contain trace amounts of lead (Green et al., 2024a).

The bioaccessibility and bioavailability of lead in game meat depends on several factors, including particle size (Barltrop and Meek, 1979) and food preparation methods. Smaller lead particles, which are more common in minced meat or after mechanical processing (Pain et al., 2023), have a higher surface area to volume ratio and are therefore more readily absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract. Cooking methods involving acidic substances, such as vinegar or wine, can further increase lead solubility and absorption. For example, studies have shown that traditional Spanish recipes using vinegar significantly increase the bioaccessibility of lead in game meat (Mateo et al., 2007; Mateo et al., 2011). Experimental studies in animals, including pigs (Hunt et al., 2009; Schulz et al., 2021) and dogs (Fernández et al., 2021), have shown that lead from game meat is bioavailable and leads to elevated blood lead levels. Dogs fed game trimmings have been shown to have significantly higher blood lead levels than dogs fed commercial pet food (Hampton et al., 2023; Rosendahl et al., 2022). Similar findings have been observed in humans, with elevated blood lead levels strongly correlating with frequent consumption of lead-shot game-birds (Green and Pain, 2012; Johansen et al., 2006) or venison (Buenz and Parry, 2018).

The health effects of lead exposure are extensive and well documented. Lead affects the nervous, cardiovascular and renal systems, with children being particularly vulnerable due to the sensitivity of their developing nervous systems (ATSDR, 2020; Cecil et al., 2008). Cognitive impairments, such as reduced IQ, are among the most serious effects in children and are considered irreversible (Cecil et al., 2008). Even low levels of lead exposure are associated with adverse outcomes, with proportionally greater effects observed at blood lead levels below 10 µg/dL. In adults, lead exposure is associated with increased blood pressure, chronic kidney disease and other systemic effects (EFSA, 2010). Frequent consumers of game meat, including hunters and their families, are at particularly high risk. Pregnant women and children are particularly vulnerable, as lead exposure during critical periods of development can have long-term effects. Therefore, in 2022, ECHA proposed to restrict lead in shooting, fishing and hunting under the EU's REACH regulation (ECHA, 2022).

The economic and social costs of lead exposure are considerable. These include direct health care costs, lost productivity due to cognitive impairment, and broader societal impacts such as increased risk of aggression and criminal behaviour (Green and Pain, 2019). Although difficult to fully monetise, these costs represent a significant burden to individuals and society. Risk assessments by organisations such as the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) have concluded that the risks of consuming wild game meat are generally low for adults, but moderate to high for children and pregnant women (ECHA, 2022). EFSA and national health authorities in several European countries have issued recommendations advising children, pregnant women and women planning to become pregnant to avoid eating game shot with lead ammunition (AESAN, 2012; Anses, 2018; BfR, 2011). Other consumers are advised to limit their intake and to avoid eating meat from severely damaged or contaminated areas of the carcass.

Reducing exposure to lead from wild game requires a multi-faceted approach. Regulatory measures, such as setting maximum allowable lead levels in game meat and banning lead ammunition, are crucial (Taggart et al., 2011; Thomas et al., 2020). Non-lead alternatives, including copper- and bismuth-based ammunition, offer a viable solution, although it is essential to ensure their safety, affordability and availability. Public awareness campaigns and hunter education programmes are essential to dispel myths about non-lead ammunition and promote safer hunting practices (Kanstrup et al., 2021). Improved meat preparation methods, such as avoiding mincing and using non-acidic cooking methods, can further reduce lead exposure. Further research on lead contamination, its health effects and the behaviour of alternative materials is also needed to inform policy and practice.

The presentation underlined the urgency of addressing lead contamination in game meat to protect public health, especially vulnerable populations such as children and pregnant women. Collaborative efforts involving policy makers, the hunting community and public health authorities are essential to achieve meaningful progress. The evidence presented provides a

compelling case for moving away from lead ammunition and implementing stricter regulations to protect human health and the environment.

The discussion following the presentation raised several critical issues, highlighting both challenges and opportunities for reducing lead contamination in game meat.

- Participants emphasised the need for standardised regulations, noting the lack of an EU-wide maximum allowable concentration for lead in game meat. Setting such limits was identified as a key step in reducing health risks, in line with existing standards for other types of meat. In addition to regulatory gaps, concerns were raised about inconsistencies in data collection and classification, such as species identification and hunting methods. Improved data quality and standardised methodologies were seen as essential for accurate risk assessment and policy making.
- The distinction between environmental contamination and ammunition-derived contamination was highlighted, particularly the accumulation of lead in the kidney and liver. It was noted that high lead concentrations in these organs may result from both environmental exposure and embedded ammunition, underscoring the complexity of interpreting contamination sources and the need for careful analysis.
- The importance of maternal and child health emerged as a key issue. Participants highlighted the lack of studies on maternal lead transfer and its effects on children in hunting families. Expanding research in this area could provide robust evidence to support public health recommendations and strengthen advocacy for the transition to lead-free ammunition.
- Discussions also touched on the benefits and challenges of non-lead alternatives, such as copper and bismuth ammunition. While these options are generally safer, concerns were raised about their fragmentation patterns and potential contamination with trace amounts of lead. Further research is needed to fully assess the safety, effectiveness and environmental impact of these materials.
- Promoting behavioural change among hunters was another key issue. Participants stressed the importance of targeted educational campaigns to dispel myths about non-lead ammunition and provide clear guidance on its use. Emphasizing the health benefits for children and future generations was highlighted as a particularly effective strategy to encourage the adoption of lead-free alternatives.

The session underlined the urgency of tackling lead contamination in wild game meat through a combination of regulatory action, public awareness and ongoing research. The scientific evidence presented during the workshop reinforced the need for immediate and coordinated efforts to reduce lead exposure, especially in vulnerable populations such as children and pregnant women.

2.2. National Reports, Reflections, and Discussion (Moderator: Rafael Mateo)

The final session of the first day, moderated by Rafael Mateo, provided a platform for participants to share national perspectives on lead ammunition regulations, reflect on the workshop discussions and identify key actions to advance the objectives of the COST Action. Contributions ranged from describing regulatory landscapes and cultural attitudes to exploring wider implications for hunting practices and game meat consumption.

National contexts and reflections

Participants shared insights into the current state of lead ammunition regulations and hunting practices in their countries. While countries such as Denmark have made significant progress in phasing out lead ammunition through comprehensive bans, other countries face slower

transitions due to inconsistent enforcement, limited awareness or cultural resistance. For example, Germany and other countries still struggle with entrenched perceptions of the superiority of lead ammunition, maintained through hunter education systems and generational traditions.

In the UK, retail pressure has driven significant change, with supermarkets increasingly demanding lead-free game meat. However, this has created challenges in the supply chain, with many producers struggling to meet the demand for lead-free game. Participants noted that such market-driven approaches, while effective, require strong industry support to ensure compliance and sustainability.

Participants also highlighted the issue of cross-border trade in game meat as an additional challenge. Wild game meat can be imported from countries where there are no regulations restricting the use of lead ammunition. This issue underlines the need for a regulatory framework to address these imports in order to ensure consumer safety.

Education and behaviour change

A recurring theme of the session was the need for targeted educational efforts to address widespread misconceptions about lead-free ammunition. Persistent myths - such as fears of damage to firearms, reduced accuracy, limited lethality or prohibitive purchase costs - continue to hinder the uptake of non-lead alternatives. Participants emphasised the importance of providing hunters with accurate, practical guidance on switching to non-lead alternatives, including information on appropriate calibres, shooting distances and safety considerations. Another key educational need highlighted during this session was to address the lack of awareness of the link between consuming game meat shot with lead ammunition, the accumulation of lead in the body, and its potential health risks. Participants noted that hunters often underestimate the dangers associated with lead residues in game meat, underscoring the importance of targeted education to bridge this knowledge gap.

Train-the-trainer programmes were suggested as a way to modernise hunter education systems, particularly in countries where younger hunters are still taught outdated practices. In addition, engaging with influencers within the hunting community and creating accessible materials, such as FAQs and how-to guides, were identified as key strategies to promote behaviour change.

Sustainability and wider impacts

The session also explored the ethical and environmental dimensions of hunting. Discussions highlighted the importance of effectively utilising game meat to ensure the sustainability of hunting practices. In many regions, significant portions of harvested animals, including offal, are left in the field, contributing to environmental contamination and secondary poisoning of scavengers such as vultures. These practices raise questions about the long-term sustainability and conservation impact of hunting.

Broader considerations included the impact of lead on wildlife populations and the potential role of game meat in promoting sustainable food systems. Participants agreed on the importance of integrating these environmental and ethical concerns into ongoing discussions on lead ammunition.

Key recommendations and future actions

The session concluded with a focus on actionable outcomes, including:

- **Regulatory development:** Participants emphasised the need for harmonised regulations across Europe, including the establishment of maximum allowable lead concentrations in game meat. Tailored limits for specific species, similar to those for farmed animals, were suggested to address variability in contamination levels.

- Educational measures: The importance of education was repeatedly stressed. Recommendations included developing practical, science-based resources for hunters, improving training programmes for new hunters, and using trusted voices within the hunting community to communicate key messages.
- Economic drivers: Addressing economic barriers to the adoption of non-lead ammunition is critical. Strategies to reduce the cost of alternatives and increase their availability, particularly in remote areas, were suggested as ways to facilitate widespread adoption.
- Stakeholder engagement: Collaborative efforts involving hunters, game meat producers, retailers and policy makers are essential. Involving these stakeholders in the development and implementation of solutions was identified as a key priority.
- Research and monitoring: Continued research into lead contamination and its health and environmental effects is essential. Participants also called for better monitoring of compliance with existing regulations and additional surveys to understand hunters' attitudes and barriers to change.
- Global coordination: Efforts to engage with international standards organisations, such as Codex Alimentarius, were seen as critical to establishing harmonised global guidelines on lead in game meat.
- Public awareness campaigns: Raising awareness of the risks associated with lead in game meat, particularly among vulnerable groups such as children and pregnant women, is necessary to build public support for regulatory and behavioural change.

Conclusion

The work of the first day of the workshop highlighted the need for a comprehensive, multi-faceted approach to tackling the problem of lead in game meat. While progress has been made in some regions, significant challenges remain to achieve widespread adoption of lead-free ammunition and to ensure the sustainability of hunting practices. Participants agreed that the COST Action provides an important framework for advancing these goals through collaboration, education and policy development. The results of this workshop will serve as a basis for future efforts to address the complex challenges related to lead contamination in the game meat chain.

3. Mitigation and Perception (Chair: Maciej Durkalec)

3.1. Mitigation Approaches: Regulations and Guidelines

(Rafael Mateo, IDAEA-CSIC, Barcelona, Spain)

The presentation addressed strategies to reduce the risks of lead contamination in game meat, focusing on regulatory measures, monitoring and consumer protection. Two main approaches were explored: eliminating lead from ammunition and regulating the presence of lead in game meat and viscera to protect consumers.

The phase-out of lead from ammunition is considered to be the most effective long-term solution. This can be achieved through voluntary conversion to lead-free ammunition or through regulatory bans. Voluntary efforts have had limited success; for example, despite a commitment by UK shooting organisations to phase out lead shot by 2025, 93% of pheasants sampled in the 2023/2024 season were still shot with lead ammunition (Green et al., 2024b). Hunters often resist change due to familiarity with the ballistic properties of lead and scepticism about its toxicity. However, regulatory measures aimed at eliminating lead from ammunition have been more effective. The EU's 2023 ban on the discharge or possession of lead shot in wetlands, including a 100-metre buffer zone, represents significant progress (EU, 2021). Historically, the number of countries banning lead shot in wetlands and uplands has steadily

increased, although enforcement and compliance remain challenges. In Spain's Ebro Delta, compliance improved only after strict enforcement measures, including the threat of hunting bans, were introduced (Mateo et al., 2014).

Regulations on lead bullets and slugs for big game are less widespread. Denmark has introduced a total ban, while other countries, including Germany and Spain, have introduced partial restrictions in specific regions or for conservation purposes (Mateo and Kanstrup, 2019). Studies of sediments in wetlands and hunting areas show the persistence of lead contamination, with densities exceeding 1 million pellets per hectare in some regions. Legacy contamination from lead ammunition in the environment remains a long-term risk, with lead persisting in soils for decades (Mateo et al., 2014).

Regulation of lead in game meat and offal is essential to protect consumers, but there are significant gaps. EU legislation sets maximum levels for other contaminants such as dioxins and PCBs in game meat, but no such limits exist for lead (European Commission, 2023). This regulatory gap leaves consumers vulnerable, especially given the high prevalence of lead fragments in wild game products, including sausages and cured meats (AESAN, 2012). Monitoring programmes are inconsistent across countries, often limited to small-scale studies rather than systematic national efforts. Quality control measures, such as metal detectors, are inadequate to detect small lead fragments (Hunt et al., 2009).

Risk communication is essential to manage the consumption of wild game meat. Examples from Canada show how clear consumption guidelines based on contaminant levels, age and demographic factors can help to reduce risks (Government of Ontario). Similar approaches for wild game could inform consumers about safe levels of consumption, particularly for children and pregnant women, who are most vulnerable to lead exposure (Anses, 2018; BfR, 2011). Studies show that consumption of even small amounts of lead-contaminated game meat can lead to adverse health effects, including reduced IQ in children and increased risk of chronic diseases in adults (EFSA, 2010).

Switching to lead-free ammunition remains the most effective strategy for reducing contamination and simplifying enforcement. However, achieving this requires harmonised regulations, stronger monitoring programmes and public education to overcome resistance and encourage compliance (Kanstrup et al., 2021; Kanstrup and Balsby, 2019; Mateo and Kanstrup, 2019).

The discussion following the presentation elaborated on these issues. Participants highlighted the difficulty of enforcing bans on lead ammunition, with compliance varying widely from region to region. Stricter enforcement measures, such as ranger surveillance and penalties, were identified as effective but resource intensive. The importance of clear, accessible risk communication was also discussed, with a call for guidelines to help consumers make informed decisions about wild meat consumption. Tailored advice for vulnerable groups, such as children and pregnant women, was highlighted as particularly important.

The role of hunters and wild meat producers in ensuring food safety was another key issue. The lack of systematic monitoring and the limitations of existing quality control measures were identified as critical gaps. The introduction of quality labels for venison shot with non-lead ammunition was suggested as a way to encourage safer practices. Participants also called for harmonised EU legislation to address differences in control and consumer protection.

The persistence of lead contamination in the environment was recognised as a long-term challenge. Even with a complete phase-out of lead ammunition, legacy contamination in soils and sediments will continue to pose risks for decades. Complementary measures, including monitoring of high-risk areas and education of hunters about these legacy risks, were identified as essential.

Participants discussed several practical challenges in addressing lead contamination in game meat. One key issue was the technical limitations of current detection methods, such as metal detectors, which often fail to identify small lead fragments, leaving gaps in quality control. Another challenge is the lack of accountability in the responsibility chain, as food business operators cannot reliably verify claims of non-lead ammunition use, and the costs of laboratory testing frequently outweigh the economic value of the game carcass. To overcome these

barriers, participants proposed incentivizing hunters and companies to adopt safer practices through economic measures or quality certification schemes. These initiatives could enhance traceability and accountability, ensuring higher standards in game meat production. Participants also noted that existing regulations generally focus on protecting the average consumer, leaving high-frequency consumers, such as hunters and their families, inadequately addressed. Developing tailored national guidelines to mitigate risks for these vulnerable groups was emphasized as an essential complement to broader regulatory measures. The session concluded with a consensus on the need for integrated approaches combining regulation, enforcement, education and stakeholder engagement. Collaboration across sectors, including policy makers, hunters, food producers and public health authorities, is essential to address the identified gaps and effectively reduce lead exposure. By applying these solutions, significant progress can be made in protecting both human health and the environment.

3.2. REACH Regulation of Lead in Outdoor Shooting and Fishing

(Dorte Bjerregaard Lerche Danish Ministry of Environment, Copenhagen, Denmark)

The presentation provided a comprehensive overview of the REACH regulation on lead in outdoor shooting and fishing. Dorte Bjerregaard Lerche looked at the current regulatory landscape, the restriction processes under REACH and the impact of the proposed restrictions on lead ammunition.

REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals) is the overarching framework for managing chemical risks in the European Union. It aims to protect human health and the environment from chemical hazards, while ensuring the competitiveness of industry and reducing animal testing. Among the 78 substances restricted under REACH as of September 2024, lead is listed for various uses, including its use in shots in wetlands.

The assessment of lead under REACH was twofold, comprising a hazard assessment and an exposure assessment. The hazard assessment highlighted the broad toxicity of lead, which affects every system in the human body, with no threshold below which it is considered safe. Critical effects include developmental effects on the central nervous system in children, where exposure at 12 µg blood-Pb/L is associated with a one IQ point loss, and chronic kidney disease in adults, with a 10% increase in prevalence associated with exposure at 15 µg blood-Pb/L. These findings highlight the significant health effects of lead exposure.

The environmental exposure assessment found that approximately 44,000 tonnes of lead are released annually in the EU from hunting, fishing and recreational shooting. Wildlife exposure occurs through the ingestion of lead shot, sinkers and baits, while indirect human exposure occurs through agricultural activities near shooting ranges and the consumption of game meat. It was estimated that approximately one million children consume lead-contaminated game meat annually, placing them at moderate to high risk.

The risk assessment identified several critical areas of concern. Hunting and sport shooting pose a high risk to birds through ingestion of lead, while consumption of game meat poses a moderate to high risk to children and the unborn child. Home-casting of lead ammunition and sinkers poses a moderate risk to human health, and lead contamination in sport shooting areas poses a high risk to soil and a moderate risk to water.

A cost-benefit analysis underlined the economic feasibility of restricting the use of lead in ammunition. The benefits, which include reduced wildlife mortality, IQ preservation in children and reduced incidence of chronic kidney disease, were estimated at €2–2.8 billion over 20 years. In comparison, the cost of implementing the restrictions over the same period was €1.1 billion, showing a favourable cost-benefit ratio.

Under the proposed REACH restriction, lead in concentrations equal to or greater than 1% by weight cannot be placed on the market or used in shotguns, other projectiles or fishing tackle. The regulation includes labelling requirements, transition periods and some exemptions, such as for historical and military use. It also emphasises the need for effective risk management measures at shooting ranges and additional voluntary efforts to collect used ammunition.

The discussion following the presentation focused on the regulatory and enforcement challenges associated with the REACH proposal. Participants expressed concern about the delay in finalising the proposal, which they attributed to political, commercial and logistical factors. The influence of hunting communities and ammunition manufacturers on the regulatory process was also identified as a potential obstacle.

The feasibility of implementing the restrictions was discussed, particularly with regard to enforcement mechanisms. Suggestions included stricter controls at the point of sale and better monitoring of ammunition use. The importance of aligning food safety legislation with environmental policy was emphasised, as was the need to comprehensively address lead contamination in game meat.

Participants acknowledged the significant costs of switching to non-lead alternatives, particularly for hunters who would need new equipment. However, it was also noted that these costs were already included in the socio-economic assessments. The discussion concluded with a call for sustained advocacy and collaborative efforts to ensure the successful implementation of the proposed restrictions.

3.3. Results of WG3 Survey on Regulation and Perception and Final Remarks (Niels Kanstrup, Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark)

The final session of the workshop was dedicated to summarising the key points raised during the two days, with a focus on summarising the discussions, assessing progress on regulatory and mitigation approaches, and planning the next steps for the COST Action initiative.

The session started with a summary of the ongoing efforts to map and analyse the status of leading mitigation approaches in the participating countries. Preliminary survey results from 18 countries highlighted the diversity of regulatory measures. Most respondents indicated a lack of legislation, while some reported national or regional legislation targeting specific habitats or species. It was noted that the recently implemented EU regulation on lead shot for wetlands had brought some consistency, but wider enforcement and compliance remained inconsistent. Responses also provided information on voluntary programmes to encourage hunters to switch to non-lead ammunition. While some countries reported initiatives to promote behaviour change, the majority noted resistance from hunters due to misconceptions about the safety, effectiveness and cost of alternatives. The lack of comprehensive data on hunter perceptions and awareness was identified as a significant gap, suggesting the need for targeted studies to better understand these dynamics.

Participants emphasised the importance of increasing survey participation to provide a more comprehensive status report. Suggestions included using official COST Action communication channels, reaching out to national hunting associations and involving scientists with established networks. The inclusion of data from countries outside Europe was also suggested to broaden the scope of the analysis.

The discussion then shifted to broader take-home messages from the workshop. Participants acknowledged the overwhelming scientific evidence on the health and environmental risks of lead from ammunition and confirmed the relevance of the objectives of the initiative. Lead was identified as the primary concern, with its well-documented toxic effects on human health, wildlife and ecosystems. It was agreed that the workshop reinforced the need for continued work to address lead contamination through regulation, education and public awareness campaigns.

Regulatory approaches were discussed in detail. It was emphasised that voluntary measures alone have proved ineffective in Europe, underlining the need for enforceable regulations. Possible measures included direct bans on lead ammunition, indirect measures such as setting maximum allowable levels of lead in game meat, and ethical considerations related to animal welfare. Participants also noted the importance of incorporating compliance mechanisms and enforcement measures into regulatory frameworks to ensure their effectiveness.

Several challenges to implementation were discussed, including the costs associated with switching to lead-free ammunition, particularly for hunters who may need to replace or modify

their firearms. Myths surrounding non-lead ammunition, such as concerns about safety, accuracy and effectiveness, were identified as significant barriers. It was suggested that communication strategies focused on dispelling these myths and emphasising the benefits of non-lead options could help to drive behaviour change.

The importance of bringing in a wider range of expertise, including social scientists, economists and communication specialists, was emphasised. Participants noted that current efforts often lack interdisciplinary perspectives, which are essential for understanding behavioural dynamics, designing effective outreach strategies, and assessing the socio-economic impacts of regulatory changes.

Finally, the discussion highlighted the need for public engagement beyond the hunting community. The role of public perception in influencing policy and market dynamics was highlighted. Participants agreed that raising awareness among non-hunters about the risks of lead in game meat and the environmental benefits of non-lead alternatives could build broader support for mitigation efforts.

In conclusion, the organisers and participants expressed their gratitude for the spirit of cooperation and high-quality discussions throughout the workshop. The meeting ended with a commitment to advance the objectives of the COST Action and to maintain the momentum in addressing the challenges associated with lead in hunting ammunition.

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